

DEVELOPMENT OF NANOCOMPOSITE MATERIAL FILMS AND INTEGRATION INTO CFRPS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL STRUCTURES

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Keywords: Carbon Nanotubes, Graphene Nanoplatelets, Nano – composites, CFRP

ABSTRACT

The performance needs originating from several industrial applications request the development of new multi - functional material that shall combine enhanced mechanical, electrical and thermal properties. Integration of nano – particles into fiber composites concludes to multi-scale reinforced composites and has opened up a new range of multifunctional materials in industry. Structural, electrical and thermal properties of nano – reinforced CFRPs promise high efficient multifunctional materials. Up to now there are certain limitations on the content of nano – particles dispersed into composite matrices. The %wt. content of nano – particles should to be kept low due to viscosity and uniform dispersion issues. A promising technique to overcome these limitations and increase the content of nano – particles into composites is to develop preformed stable structures of nano - particles and integrate them to conventional fiber reinforced composites. Nano – particle films are stable preformed structures that could be integrated into composite materials and enhance their multifunctionality depending upon the nano - particles used to manufacture the films.

In this work Multiwall Carbon Nanotube (MWCNT) films and hybrid films with MWCNTs and Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNPs) were fabricated. The nano – materials dispersed into distilled water with polymer dispersants and mixed using sonication to form uniform and stable aqueous dispersions. The nano – particle films prepared using a casting method. These polymer based self – supported nanomaterial films were used also as integrated interleaves into CFRPs in order to enhance electrical and thermal conductivity.

Scanning Electron Microscopy used to evaluate the internal structure of the polymer based nanoparticle films. Tensile tests performed to the nanoparticle films to measure their mechanical properties. Surface Electrical Conductivity was also measured using a 4-point measurement method; the results are promising for the electrical applications of these materials (e.g. self-sensing materials, lightning strike protection systems, energy storage devices). Finally Thermal Conductivity tests performed to evaluate their thermal performance and also their influence on the thermal properties of the composite materials.

The next step of the work involves the introduction of the polymer based nanoparticle films into CFRP laminates. Cross ply CFRPs were manufactured and mechanical characterization together with electrical and thermal conductivity measurement were performed.

1 INTRODUCTION

The incorporation of micro- and nano-phase in polymers to improve material performance has been a concept since the early '90s. When carbon nanotubes (CNT) were reported, an interest to revisit the field was triggered. The use of nano – reinforcements in polymer composites has produced improvements in multiple structural functions and non – structural functions. The most important structural functions of a system are stiffness, strength, fracture toughness, energy absorption, damping and thermal stability while very important non – structural functions are electrical and thermal conductivity, sensing and structural health monitoring (SHM), actuation, energy harvesting/storage, electromagnetic interference shielding (EMI), self – healing capability etc. For example, small concentrations of CNTs (~0.3% wt.) in epoxy matrix glass fiber composites could lead to 20% enhancement of ILSS properties while exhibiting an in – plane conductivity which could be useful for life monitoring applications [1].

For composite structures, however, the approach of developing nano-modified polymers and use them consequently as matrices to produce for Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP) [2] [3] was the tipping point in this technology. In essence the concept of nano-reinforced composites is the development of multi-scale reinforced polymers (Fig. 1). In the same material system three different phases co-exist; the host polymer, the macro reinforcement (continuous carbon fibres) and the nano-scale reinforcement (e.g. CNT). This approach promises composite materials with enhanced performance and the capability for integrated functionalities - multifunctionality approach [4]. This approach has also been referred to as hierarchical composites [5]. These novel hierarchical or hybrid composite systems may benefit from the advantages of traditional structural composites and, at the same time, gain in properties and functionalities from the incorporation of the nano – scale reinforcement as additive in the composite material structure.

Figure 1: SEM Micrograph of multi-scale reinforced composite.

Several approaches for the utilization of nanotechnology in structural composite structures have been proposed in literature. There are two main routes to introduce nano – enabled composites, Nano – augmentation, meaning the randomly and homogeneously dispersing nano – particles into the matrix of the composite material, and Nano – engineering, meaning the use of pre – organized nano – particle structures introducing them in the composite laminate [6].

Nowadays, there is a very wide field of nano – technologies with a great variety of nano – materials from carbon allotropes to ceramic and metal based nano – particles applied to structural composites for the enhancement of their mechanical, thermal, electrical performance and their multifunctionality. The most common idea for the development of CNT doped fibre composites is that of bulk random dispersion of CNT in the matrix of the composite. The dispersion of the raw nanomaterials, like CNT powder or GNPs, into the matrix prior to impregnation can produce a homogeneous distribution that can maximize the effective interface area between the carbon nano - phase and the matrix. This approach is a typical nano – augmentation technique by the use of nano – particles in the form of powder as a raw material but up to now there are certain limitations on the content of nano – particles

dispersed into composite matrices. The %wt. content of nano – particles should to be kept low due to viscosity and uniform dispersion issues.

To overcome these limitations, a systemically different approach is the introduction of nano-phase through nano – particle preforms. 2D CNT preforms are available like CNT sheets, or as called Buckypapers [7], which can be impregnated during the first stages of the curing. Also, Buckypapers with hybrid formulations of nano – particles has been proposed in literature [8]. Finally, other alternative approaches require preprocessing of the raw materials, like preprocessing of the fibre forms. For example an approach is to grow CNTs on the fibres in the radial direction.

In this work investigated another approach, to bring the nano – phase reinforcement in self – standing film form and integrate into the composite structure during lamination to enhance the electrical and thermal conductivity. Multiwall Carbon Nanotube (MWCNT) films and hybrid films with MWCNTs and Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNPs) were fabricated and integrated during the lamination process of CFRP composite structures, an additional step is required for this approach for the formation of the nano – particle film prior to the composite manufacturing where aqueous nano - particle suspensions formed by CNT aqueous dissolved solid concentrates and GNPs in powder form. The nano – particles dispersed on distilled water with polymer dispersants and mixed using sonication until the formation of a uniform suspension. Then, low amount of Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) as polymer binder added to the uniform solution to ensure the self – standing behavior of the nano – particle film and finally the solution left over a polymer substrate until the complete evaporation of the water and the final formation of the film. After the formation of this polymer based nano – particle film several layers were cut and introduced to the composite structure during lamination. The CFRP composites manufactured by Infusion of liquid epoxy to CFRP - nano – particle preform.

2 MATERIALS

Aqueous dissolved Multiwall Carbon Nanotube solid particle concentrates was obtained by Arkema (CW2 – 42, 45% wt. MWCNT, 55% wt. Carboxylmethylcellulose) with 10 to 15 walls and 12 nm mean diameter. Graphene Nanoplatelets with 24 layers, surface area 100 m²/gr, diameter 5 µm and thickness 10 nm were obtained by Cheaptubes in powder form. Polyvinylpyrrolidone was obtained by Sigma Aldrich (K 60, 45% in H₂O, Mr ~160000). For the dispersion of the nano – particles used distilled water.

For the manufacturing composites used Carbon Fibre plain fabric with areal weight 160 g/m² obtained by Fibermax Composites and the Epoxy Resin system used was MVR444 by Advanced Composites Group Ltd. suitable for infusion.

3 CHARACTERIZATION

3.1 NANO – PARTICLE FILMS

For the microstructural analysis of the nano – particle films Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) used (Zeiss SUPRA 35VP operating at 30 KV) on small samples cut from the films along thickness direction. Several micrographs captured in different magnifications and the dimensions and the dispersion of the nano – particles evaluated.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) used to determine the thermal transition states of these polymer based nano – particle films from room temperature to 300 °C and melting point and glass transition temperature were identified (DuPont Instruments 910 series).

Mechanical properties of the nano – particle films investigated with tensile tests for thin plastic sheets performed according to ASTM D882 with samples dimensions 150 mm length and 25 mm width. An INSTRON 8872 - 25kN Servo-hydraulic Universal Testing Machine used with the crosshead speed adjusted at 0.1 mm/min and tensile modulus and strength calculated.

Electrical conductivity measured using the 4 – point method. Four electrodes were pressed to the film surface and the resistance was measured by a KEITHLEY DMM 2002 multimeter. The resistance measured translated to surface resistance and specific resistance and then surface electrical conductivity.

3.2 FIBRE COMPOSITES

For the quality assessment of the composite plates ultrasonic C – Scan performed to assess the continuity, uniformity and presence of air voids in the laminate. The ultrasonic system used is an AD-IPR 1210 board (100 MHz sampling rate @ 12 bit resolution, NDT Automation - MISTRAS) along with a X-Y positioning system (VUB2000). The software for the data and image capture is ULTRAWIN and the transducer is a non-focal, 5 MHz KRAUTKRAMMER immersion probe.

Macroscopic structure analysis of the cross-section of the fibre composite materials performed using Light Optical Microscopy (LOM). Samples from the composite material cut and examined with LOM to investigate the interaction of the nano – particle films in the structure of the composite. Further investigation will be done focusing on any observed defects (e.g. microcracks).

Microscopic structure investigation and micro – nano interface mechanisms evaluated using SEM. Several micrographs captured in different magnifications and areas along thickness and surface of the composite in the area where nano – particle incorporates with the composite.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis testing performed following ASTM-D5418 using a DuPont Instruments Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer 983. The objective of the test is to estimate a first indication of the elastic modulus of the produced laminate material and identify the glass transition temperature (T_g). Additionally, this test will be used as an initial evaluation of the material's damping properties with the evaluation of the $\tan(\delta)$. Rectangular samples with dimensions 44.5 mm length, 6.4 mm width and 2 mm thickness cut for the purpose of the test.

The electrical conductivity of the composite materials in the through the thickness direction (Z) defined by a four probe station equipped with a KEITHLEY DMM 2002 multimeter. Samples with dimensions 40 mm by 40 mm with 2 mm thickness cut and their surface treated with grinding and silver paint to avoid any contact defects.

Thermal conductivity of the nano – particle films measured by a TCi Mathis thermal conductivity analyzer based on the modified transient plane source technique. Specimens of 30 x 30 x 2 mm in size were placed on a one – side sensor. An electrical current is applied to the sensor's heating element that provides a small amount of heat. The temperature increases at the interface between sample and sensor and induces a change in the voltage drop of the sensor element. The rate of increase in the sensor voltage leads to the calculation of specimen's thermal diffusivity and conductivity.

4 MANUFACTURING

4.1 NANO – PARTICLE FILMS

MWCNT solid concentrates (pellets) dispersed in distilled water. The amount of MWCNT pellets per weight should be kept below 6% wt according to the supplier instructions. Magnetic stirring is applied to the mixture until the uniform dispersion of the pellets at constant temperature of 70 °C temperature. Then the mixture suffers ultrasonication mixing with an ultrasonication probe for 1 hour with a power of 80 watts to brake all MWCNT agglomerates. Then in the mixture added low amount (<5% wt.) of the polymer binder (PVP), that ensures the self – standing nature of the nano – particle film, and stirred with a magnetic stirrer until the formation of a uniform solution with increased viscosity. In the case of hybrid formulation of nano – particles, the GNPs are added to the mixture before ultrasonication. After the preparation of the mixture the solution is casted over a polymer substrate with a doctor blade having the blade adjusted at 1 mm height. Finally, the casted solution remains on the polymer substrate until the complete evaporation of water. This technique produces a high amount (~40% wt.) polymer nano – particle self - standing film with thickness 60 – 70 μm . In this work produced two different nano – particle films with ~40% wt. amount of nano – particles. One with 100% MWCNTs in the nano – particle formulation and one with hybrid formulation 70/30% MWCNTs/GNPs. Areal weight measured right after manufacturing of the films.

Sample ID	Nano-particle content %wt.	Areal Weight (gsm)
<i>MWCNT/PVP film</i>	36%	125 (±30)
<i>MWCNT/GNP/PVP film (Hybrid)</i>	38% (70/30 MWCNT/GNP)	97 (±12.5)

Table 1: Nano – particle films list.

Figure 2: MWCNT/PVP film after manufacturing.

4.2 FIBRE COMPOSITES

Nano – particle film layers used to fabricate laminate composites with carbon fibre fabric and epoxy resin. The technique used for the fabrication of the composites was an Infusion technique. 10 layers of carbon fabric with four layers of nano – particle film in cross - ply lamination sequence impregnated under vacuum with epoxy resin. The epoxy resin kept at 100 °C to lower its viscosity. After complete impregnation of the fibre nano – particle preform the composite plates polymerized at 120 °C under vacuum pressure.

Samlpe ID	Lay - up.
<i>Reference CFRP</i>	10 layers carbon fabric, cross ply
<i>Nano - Composite CFRP</i>	10 layers carbon fabric, cross ply + 4 layers of Hybrid Nano – particle film

Table 2: Composite plates list.

Figure 3: Infusion of epoxy resin.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 NANO – PARTICLE FILMS

Microstructural Analysis of the nano – particle films performed via scanning electron microscopy. By the micrographs captured at different magnification levels from approximately 1000x to 30000x and the internal structure of the nano – particles in both films was found uniform. The nano – particles were distributed uniformly in the structure of the nano – particle polymer film. CNT agglomerates were not observed into the structure. Also and in the case of hybrid nano – particle formulation the GNPs and CNTs were uniform distributed in the film structure, which is critical for taking advantage of the synergistic effect [9]. Also, agglomerates of the polymer binder (PVP) were not observed.

a) *MWCNT/PVP film:*

Figure 4: SEM micrographs of MWCNT/PVP film at ~850x showing the cross – section of the film and at 10Kx showing an overview of the internal structure and distribution of the nano – particles.

Figure 5: SEM micrographs at ~30Kx showing a closer view of the CNTs in the structure of the film.

The diameter of the CNTs measured at different areas of the film to evaluate the effect of the polymer dispersant and polymer binder on their dimensions. The average diameter measured at approximately 23 nm when the CNT diameter indicated by the manufacturer of the CNTs is around 12 nm.

b) *MWCNT/GNP/PVP film:*

Figure 6: SEM micrographs of MWCNT/GNP/PVP film at ~1Kx showing the cross – section of the film and at 10Kx showing an overview of the internal structure and distribution of the nano – particles, CNTs and GNPs distributed in the film structure.

Figure 7: SEM micrographs at ~30Kx showing a closer view of the CNTs and GNPs in the structure of the film.

Also in this case the CNT diameters after manufacturing of the film was measured. Mean diameter measured at 24 nm. By the micrographs captured it is shown that the CNTs have attached to the surface of the GNPs creating CNT network around them, critical factor for effective contribution of the synergistic effect on the final film properties.

Thermoanalytical characterization of the nano – composite films performed by Differential Scanning Calorimetry from room temperature to 250 °C to evaluate the polymer binder behavior in the film and how is affected by the presence of the nano – particles in the structure. Critical value for the manufacturing of the composite plates is the melting point of the polymer binder. The curing process of the composite should be performed in temperature over the melting temperature of the nano – composite film polymer binder so the nano – particles to be delivered on the composite plate structure. In both nano - composite films the melting point found around the theoretical value of the melting point of PVP at 100 – 110 °C with common behavior. So, polymer binder thermoanalytical behavior did not affected by the presence of the nano – particles.

Figure 8: Nano – composite films DSC behavior from room temperature to 250 °C.

Mechanical properties of polymer films measured using tensile tests according to the ASTM D882 that describes the method for measuring mechanical properties of thin plastic films under tensile. Elastic modulus and tensile strength of the nano – composite films measured. Nano – composite films with hybrid formulation (70/30 MWCNT/GNP) shown better mechanical behavior with higher tensile strength and elastic modulus, tensile strength of the hybrid nano – composite film measured at 40.5 MPa and tensile modulus at 5.6 GPa when for the MWCNT film the tensile strength measured at 35.7 MPa and tensile modulus at 4.6 GPa. The breakage of the nano – composite films occurred at strain 1% ($\pm 0.2\%$).

Figure 9: Mechanical properties of the nano – composite films. Tensile strength in the left side of the figure and tensile modulus at the right side of the figure.

Finally, surface electrical conductivity measured for the nano – composite films by a four point probe method. Hybrid nano – composite has higher values of electrical conductivity, almost 100% by the MWCNT film. The synergistic effect between the MWCNTs and the GNPs distributed the electrical load more efficiently in the structure of the film. Surface electrical conductivity of the MWCNT film measured at 510 S/m and electrical conductivity of the hybrid film measured at 964 S/m.

Figure 10: Surface Electrical Conductivity results for the nano – composite films.

5.2 FIBRE COMPOSITES

Quality inspection via ultrasonics scanning of the composite plates performed after manufacturing to evaluate the impact of the nano – composite in the structure of the composite. The composites manufacturing performed using Infusion of liquid resin and it is critical to confirm that the presence of the nano - composite films does not affect the resin impregnation of the carbon fabrics during the Infusion process. The distribution of the epoxy resin in the composites was uniform in both cases. The impregnation of the carbon fabrics with nano – composite films into the preform structure of the composite proved feasible and the produced composite plate proceed to further characterization.

Figure 11: Ultrasonics inspection (C – Scan) of the composite plates.

Samples cut for optical microscopy and macroscopic analysis of the internal structure of the composites. The interaction of the nano – composite film in the composite laminate was examined. Defects that could be caused by the presence of the nano – composite film did not observed. Also, by the micrographs captured the fiber volume fraction of the composite laminates was measured. The fiber volume fraction of the nano – composite CFRP laminate measured at 45% (+5%) and for the reference CFRP laminate measured at 40% (+5).

Figure 12: Optical microscopy micrographs captured at magnification 20x for both composite laminates. At the right side of the figure the nano – composite CFRP laminate with two layers of hybrid film.

Further examination of the internal structure of the nano - composite laminate was performed by using Scanning Electron Microscopy. Fractured sample of the laminate were also investigated at the area of the nano – composite film in order to examine the interaction of the nano – particles with carbon fibres. Distributed nano – particles observed on the carbon fibres, fact that proves that the nano – composite film after manufacturing at temperature over the melting point of the polymer binder is feasible to deliver the nano – phase at the surface carbon – fibre. Also, in fractured areas it was observed nano – particles pulled out operating as crack – bridging elements. Further investigation for this phenomenon should be studied in future works.

Figure 13: Micrographs captured at 15Kx (a,b) showing distribution of the nano – particles (CNTs and GNPs) over the carbon fibre surface and at 20Kx (c,d) CNTs and GNPs observed that have been pulled out at the fractured area.

The electrical conductivity of the composite laminates measured in the through the thickness direction. Electrical conductivity increased by 20% in the case of the nano – composite laminates form 3.5 S/m to 4.3 S/m.

Figure 14: Electrical conductivity through z-axis measurements results of composite laminates.

Also the contribution of the nano – composite films on the thermal conductivity in the through the thickness direction measured. The thermal conductivity increased by 20% from 0.70 W/mK to 0.85 W/mK.

Figure 15: Thermal conductivity results through z-axis of the composite laminates.

Finally, as it is shown at Figure 16 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of the reference and the nano – modified laminates was performed in order to monitor the variation of bending stiffness of the examined laminates versus temperature, for a temperature range from ambient temperature up to 300 °C. At ambient temperature the nano – modified laminate appeared lower bending stiffness compared to the reference laminate of about 5%.

As temperature increases the reference laminate keeps its stiffness almost constant and it starts to decrease rapidly approaching the T_g . In contrast to this behavior, the nano – modified laminate appears a constant decrease of bending stiffness from very low temperature of about 80 °C. This stiffness decrease is associated to the presence of the polymeric binder (PVP) of the carbon based nano – species which has very low T_g and degrades the bonding between the laminate layers as temperature increases.

It is important to notice that further to the stiffness degradation versus temperature in the case of nano – modified laminates, the T_g of this laminates drops of about 20 °C. Furthermore, the nano – modified laminate appears significantly higher damping characteristics ($\tan\delta$) compared against the reference laminate. This damping increase is at the level of 30%.

Figure 16: Thermomechanical behavior of the composite laminates (DMA).

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this work another approach for integrating nano – particles in composite hierarchical material is investigated. Successfully fabricated nano – composite polymer based flexible self – standing films with high content of nano – particles (~40%) with MWCNTs and hybrid nano – particle formulation of MWCNTs and GNPs and integrated to composite laminates as interleaves made by Infusion process. Electrical and thermal conductivity increased by 20% for the final nano – composite CFRP laminate. Mechanical degradation in terms of bending stiffness observed exclusively at temperatures over 80 °C but damping performance was improved. Further research should be performed to evaluate the mechanical performance under different loading of the hierarchical composites produced with nano – composite interleaves. Also, variety of nano – particles should be tested and connected in respect with their applications. Finally, the selection of the polymer additives (dispersants, binders etc.) in the structure of the nano – composite film should be carefully selected considering their compatibility with the polymer matrix of the final composite material.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the present work by the European Union (European Social Fund - ESF) and the Greek national funds executed by the Greek Secretariat for Research & Technology within the frame of bilateral cooperation between Greece and Germany under the activity with the acronym GRACE.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. H. Gojny, M. H. G. Wichmann, B. Fiedler, W. Bauhofer, and K. Schulte, "Influence of nano-modification on the mechanical and electrical properties of conventional fibre-reinforced composites," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 36, no. 11, pp. 1525–1535, Nov. 2005.
- [2] T. Mahrholz, J. Mosch, D. Röstermundt, U. Riedel, L. Herbeck, and M. Sinapius, "Fibre-reinforced nanocomposites for spacecraft structures manufacturing, characterisation and application," *Eur. Sp. Agency, (Special Publ. ESA SP)*, no. 581, pp. 1445–1454, 2005.

- [3] E. Kostopoulos V., Baltopoulos A., Vavouliotis A., Sotiriadis G., Fiamegkou, C. Kostagiannakopoulou, and A. Masouras, "NANOTECHNOLOGIES FOR STRUCTURAL COMPOSITE MATERIALS Review of latest research developments and open challenges towards application, 8th ESA Micro-Nanotechnology Round Table, ESA/ESTEC, Noordwijk," no. October, pp. 1–32, 2012.
- [4] V. Kostopoulos, a. Vavouliotis, P. Karapappas, P. Tsotra, and a. Paipetis, "Damage Monitoring of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Laminates Using Resistance Measurements. Improving Sensitivity Using Carbon Nanotube Doped Epoxy Matrix System," *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.*, vol. 20, no. 9, pp. 1025–1034, 2009.
- [5] H. Qian, E. S. Greenhalgh, M. S. P. Shaffer, and A. Bismarck, "Carbon nanotube-based hierarchical composites: a review," *J. Mater. Chem.*, vol. 20, no. 23, p. 4751, 2010.
- [6] A. Paipetis, V. Kostopoulos, A. Vavouliotis, P. Karapappas, P. Tsotra, C. Jaillet, N. D. Alexopoulos, P. Poulin, S. Grishchuk, R. Schledjewski, D. Giliopoulos, K. Triantafyllidis, D. Gournis, T. C. Theodosiou, D. A. Saravanos, and N.-M. Barkoula, *Carbon Nanotube Enhanced Aerospace Composite Materials*. Springer, 2013.
- [7] Z. Wang, Z. Liang, B. Wang, C. Zhang, and L. Kramer, "Processing and property investigation of single-walled carbon nanotube (SWNT) buckypaper/epoxy resin matrix nanocomposites," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 1225–1232, Oct. 2004.
- [8] A. Baltopoulos, V. Kostopoulos, A. Vavouliotis, and S. Elefthriou, "Development of Hybrid Buckypaper (HBP) Structures and multi-functional assessment of composites incorporating HBP," in *14th European Conference on Composite Materials, ECCM 14*, 2010.
- [9] C. Kostagiannakopoulou, G. Maroutsos, G. Sotiriadis, A. Vavouliotis, and V. Kostopoulos, "Study on the synergistic effects of graphene/carbon nanotubes polymer nanocomposites," in *Third International Conference on Smart Materials and Nanotechnology in Engineering*, 2012, p. 840911.